

IDENTIFICATION OF LOW-FREQUENCY OSCILLATIONS OF PARAMETERS IN POWER SYSTEMS USING NON-PARAMETRIC METHODS OF REAL-TIME SIGNAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Over recent decades, low-frequency oscillations in operating parameters have caused a number of major incidents in power systems and unions. The consolidation and expansion of these systems and unions increases the risk of low-frequency oscillations arising within them, due to the emergence of new interconnections, power equipment with inappropriate settings, and so on.

To enable the timely detection of risks to the oscillatory instability of power systems and unions, problem-oriented monitoring systems require access to relevant real-time information on the frequencies and damping coefficients of the dominant modes of low-frequency oscillations.

This article presents the results of research into the feasibility of applying non-parametric signal analysis methods to determine the parameters of low-frequency oscillations in electrical parameters in real time.

Keywords: low-frequency oscillations, real-time signal analysis, non-parametric methods.

Introduction

The occurrence of low-frequency oscillations in power systems and unions poses a risk of interconnections being disconnected and of the power equipment in these systems and unions ceasing to operate in parallel. To prevent such situations, the processes leading to the occurrence and development of low-frequency oscillations in power systems and interconnections must be constantly monitored.

The algorithms used by low-frequency oscillation monitoring systems are often based on determining the eigenvalues of power systems and unions, which are calculated from the results of studies of their computer models. At the same time, it is often impossible to obtain up-to-date and complete information on the status of the electrical connection diagrams of equipment, its configuration parameters, operational status and the settings of automatic process control systems in power systems and unions. This may be due to equipment damage or failure, disruptions to communication channels caused by natural or human factors, and so on. In such a situation, the calculation of eigenvalues to identify the risk of low-frequency oscillations in power systems and unions may yield distorted results, which, in turn, will lead to an inadequate assessment of the risk of oscillatory instability in their parallel operation.

Another approach to providing the information component of monitoring systems for low-frequency oscillations is to use signals indicating changes over time in the operating parameters of power system objects and interconnections – such as voltage, current, active power, and so on. With this approach, in order to promptly detect the threat of a loss of oscillatory stability in the parallel operation of power systems and interconnections, it is necessary to ensure rapid analysis of these signals, determining the amplitudes and damping factors of the dominant modes of these oscillations in real time. Various signal analysis methods can be used to carry out such an analysis – Fourier transform, non-parametric and parametric methods, wavelet transform, Stockwell transform, Hilbert–Huang transform, etc [1].

The aim of this article is to investigate the possibility of using non-parametric analysis methods to determine the parameters of low-frequency oscillations in real time.

Non-parametric methods of signal analysis

Non-parametric methods of signal analysis make no assumptions regarding the model of the signal under analysis when calculating its spectrum; therefore, its parameters are determined solely on the basis of the information contained in the signal readings. Non-parametric methods of analysis include the periodogram, the spectrogram, and the Welch and Thomson methods [2].

A periodogram is an estimate of the spectral power density (SPD) obtained from N samples of a single realisation of a random process by averaging a finite number of terms. The periodogram is calculated as follows [2]:

$$W(\omega) = \frac{1}{N \cdot f_d} \cdot \left| \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x(k) \cdot e^{-j \cdot \omega \cdot k \cdot T} \right|^2, \quad (1)$$

where:

$x(k)$ – discrete signal;

ω – angular frequency;

f_d – signal sampling rate;

N – number of signal readings;

k – harmonic component number;

T – signal period.

Expression (1) bears a certain similarity to the expression defining the discrete Fourier transform [2], but, due to the squaring of the expansion coefficients, the dominant frequencies will be highlighted more clearly when constructing a periodogram than when using the discrete Fourier transform.

In order to calculate the SPD using a modified periodogram, weighting functions (windows) with coefficients $w(k)$ are applied:

$$W_m(\omega) = \frac{1}{f_d} \cdot \frac{\left| \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x(k) \cdot w(k) \cdot e^{-j \cdot \omega \cdot k \cdot T} \right|^2}{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |w(k)|^2}. \quad (2)$$

The use of weighting functions allows to reduce the high-frequency components of the spectrum, which may be caused by noise (interference) present in the signal.

An important feature of the periodogram is that it cannot be used to obtain an adequate estimate of the signal's mean square error, as the variance of such an estimate may be close to the square of its mathematical expectation, regardless of the number of samples N in the signal data set. This characteristic of the periodogram significantly reduces its suitability for determining the parameters of low-frequency oscillation components in real time.

A spectrogram is an instantaneous, time-dependent spectrum of a signal. To calculate a spectrogram, the signal is divided into segments, for each of which a fast Fourier transform is computed. To illustrate how the amplitude of the signal spectrum changes over time, a graphical representation of the spectrogram is usually plotted in time–frequency (t – f) coordinates, although graphs of the amplitude spectrum in frequency–amplitude (f – A) coordinates can also be produced. The spectrogram of a given signal is calculated as follows [2]:

$$S(t, \omega) = |WFT(t, \omega)|^2, \quad (3)$$

where:

$WFT(t, \omega)$ – window function Fourier transform [3].

The use of the windowed Fourier transform when calculating a spectrogram makes it possible to improve the quality of the frequency spectrum calculation at the boundaries of the observation window.

The Welch method is a modification of the periodogram (2). It differs from the periodogram in that it divides the signal's time-domain vector into overlapping segments, multiplies each segment by a specific weighting function, and then calculates a modified periodogram (due to the application of the weighting function) for each segment before averaging them. The number of segments recommended for the Welch method should be a multiple of 2. Given the limitations of the fast Fourier transform, this number should not be too large, as this significantly reduces the resolution of the Welch method.

The use of weighting functions for signal segments in the Welch method makes it possible, compared with the periodogram method, to improve the quality of the frequency spectrum calculation by reducing spectrum smearing, whilst the use of overlapping signal segments reduces the variance of the estimation results.

The Thomson method (or Multitaper method) is used to calculate the spectrum of a signal using l modified (by means of weighting functions) periodograms $g_{l,n}$, each of which is obtained using different Slepian sequences:

$$S_k(f) = \Delta t \cdot \left| \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} g_{l,n} \cdot x_n \cdot e^{-j \cdot \omega \cdot k \cdot \Delta t} \right|^2, \quad (4)$$

where:

Δt – time interval between samples in a signal data set.

The Thomson method is free from some of the limitations of the discrete Fourier transform – in particular, it provides a more accurate determination of the relative phases for each frequency component of the signal under analysis.

Requirements for signal analysis methods to ensure reliable identification of dominant modes of low-frequency oscillations in real time

The results of the author's research [4, 5] make it possible to formulate the following requirements for signal analysis methods in terms of their suitability for use in determining the parameters of the dominant modes of low-frequency oscillations in real time:

1. The adequacy of identification and the accuracy of determining the parameters of the dominant modes of low-frequency oscillations due to the fact that the effective operation of damping devices depends on the accuracy of determining the dominant frequencies.

2. High frequency resolution due to the possibility of the existence in the power system or union of a combination of several vibration modes at closely spaced frequencies (for example, in Mexican power system with the frequencies of 0,32 Hz, 0,52 Hz, 0,62 Hz, 0,77 Hz and 0,92 Hz [6]).

3. The reliability of detecting low-frequency oscillations in a signal and determining the parameters of their dominant modes due to the need of identification of the dominant modes even with small amplitudes and to ensure resilience to noises (interferences) present in real signals.

4. High responsiveness, necessitated by the need to prevent oscillatory instability in the power system or power union arising from the onset and rapid development of low-frequency oscillations.

An important feature of the real-time mode for determining the parameters of low-frequency oscillation modes is the need to analyse samples of signal data, the set of which is periodically updated on a "first in – first out" basis.

The width of the observation window used during signal analysis with a particular method must be sufficient to yield adequate analysis results and, at the same time, must cover the shortest possible time interval, to ensure the necessary speed in identifying the dominant modes of low-frequency oscillations and assessing the presence of a threat to the operation of the power system or power union. In view of this, the number of signal samples within a given observation window and, accordingly, the duration (length) of the time interval covered by the observation window may vary both for different signal analysis methods and for different signal data samples corresponding to different operating modes of the power system or power union.

Results of testing non-parametric signal analysis methods with regard to application for the real-time detection of low-frequency oscillations

The testing of signal analysis methods was carried out using a synthesised three-component test signal with constant component amplitudes, described by the equation $y(t) = 100 + 2\sin(2\pi \cdot 0,1t) + 1\sin(2\pi \cdot 0,2t)$.

The test signal contains components with frequencies of 0,1 Hz and 0,2 Hz, which correspond to typical modes of low-frequency oscillations in power systems. To test signal analysis methods, a data set with a sampling rate of 50 Hz was used, with a time window covering the interval 0–10 s (a section of the test signal graphic is shown in Fig. 1). Testing signal analysis methods using a longer time window is not advisable, given the dynamics of changes in the amplitude of low-frequency oscillations when they occur in power systems or power pools.

The results of identifying the low-frequency components of the test signal using a periodogram,

a spectrogram, and the Welch and Thomson methods, carried out on the basis of (2)–(4), are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. A section of the test signal graphic

Figure 2. Results of the identification of low-frequency components of the test signal

During the calculations, no weighting functions (windows) were applied, which reduced the number of factors that could influence the results of the analysis. In order to calculate the SPD of the test signal data sample using a spectrogram and the Welch method, the data sample was divided into 8 segments with the maximum possible overlap between them to ensure the highest possible resolution of the tested signal analysis methods.

Conclusions

Analysis of the graphics in Fig. 2 showed that the non-parametric signal analysis methods under consideration were unable to identify components with frequencies of 0,1 Hz and 0,2 Hz in the 10-second test signal data set, which is due to the limitation imposed by the frequency resolution of the discrete Fourier transform, on which the methods under consideration are based.

Furthermore, the SPD plots obtained using the non-parametric signal analysis methods discussed do not correspond to the actual SPD plot of the test signal,

as the sample of this signal does not contain any components with a frequency above 0,2 Hz.

Therefore, given the requirements for signal analysis methods, in view of their potential application for determining the parameters of low-frequency oscillations in the operating parameters of power systems and unions in real time, and taking into account the results of the study conducted, it can be concluded that the use of periodograms, spectrograms, and the Welch and Thomson methods for this purpose is not feasible.

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